

Cognitive and Emotive language

Cognitive and Emotive language

Introduction

Cognitive Language is a way of communicating significant information. Words have cognitive meaning when they convey information. Human capacity that we are all born with allows us to learn and use at least one communication system. The language is predominantly a function of the left hemisphere (Walton et.al, 2014). But also the right hemisphere has a bit of language. One of the earliest things discovered about the brain were the speech centers: Broca's area and Wernicke's area, which is where we understand the meaning of language, another important part is the angular rotation that serves as a connection between the language centers, the visual cortex and motor cortex. Emotive language is designed to elicit a strong emotional response. Words are chosen for the possible consequences for emotions, rather than simply as facts clearly. It is sometimes used to pass something as fact without facts to support the claim (Kazemifard et.al, 2012, p 24).

Discussion

Cognitive Language convey information like this sentence "The sun went up, the stars faded out, all the dark disappeared into scheduled gray. A buzzing sound crowded out the still night air. It has cognitive meaning which is conveying information related to some subject. Another example of cognitive language is "The normal figure of sex partners per person has remained fairly steady over the past years. Many adults usually had only one partner in last 5 years, which is more than two-thirds, had only one partner in the past year (Rabin, et.al, 2011, p. 1).

Emotive Language is used when the speaker (sender) uses language to express their feelings or reflect a subjective attitude: (Kazemifard et.al, 2012, p 24)

How sorry! O what a shame!

In some cases, you are allowed to use both question marks as admiration in one sentence. For example You did not do your homework!

You see, prayer begins having a phobic function, but ends up expressing disgust or surprise for not meeting the other with his duty. Thus, although the question mark corresponds not express feelings, it can be combined with other signs to express them. In fact, the context is crucial to define the function (Kazemifard et.al, 2012, p 24). Example of Emotive statement like “This was one of the most horrible big budget movie theater I’ve seen. The show were cringe-inducing, the writing was immature, and the special effects were low financially plan. Embarrassing all around.”

Conclusion

The results indicate that those who speak two or more languages had significantly better cognitive abilities compared to what was expected by his intellectual level in childhood. The strongest effects were in general intelligence and reading skills. The phenomenon is found both in those who learned a second language before the age of 18 years, and who did so at a later age. To sum some meaning is to convey both language emotive and cognitive like this statement “Ahead of New Deal, the Great Society, Obamacare, and other socialist garbage, patients just rewarded their health center (Kazemifard et.al, 2012, p 24). The expenses were less than they are today, and my family and I were never say no. You had appalling insurance to cover

catastrophes, and it was affordable and it paid health center. The organization worked and administration meddlers and bureaucrats have just mucked this up.

References

Walton, D., & Macagno, F. (2014). *Emotive Language in Argumentation*. Cambridge University Press.

Kazemifard, M., Ghasem-Aghaee, N., & Ören, T. I. (2012). Emotive and cognitive simulations by agents: Roles of three levels of information processing. *Cognitive Systems Research, 13*(1), p. 24-38.

Rabin, B., Burdea, G., Hundal, J., Roll, D., & Damiani, F. (2011, June). Integrative motor, emotive and cognitive therapy for elderly patients chronic post-stroke A feasibility study of the BrightArm™ rehabilitation system. In *Virtual Rehabilitation (ICVR), 2011 International Conference on* (p. 1-8). IEEE.